

Quality of Nursing Care Toward Patients Admitted to General Surgical Wards in Selected Governmental Teaching Hospitals in Sudan: Across -Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Quality nursing care plays a vital role for patients because nurses are involved in almost every aspect of client care in the hospital. The quality of services mostly depends on nursing care because they spend more time with patients to care for their better health.

Objective: To assess the quality of nursing care towards patients admitted to general surgical wards in selected governmental teaching hospitals in Sudan.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional hospital-based study conducted in three governmental teaching hospitals from 2022 to 2023. The study included 95 patients selected by convenience sampling techniques. Data were collected through an observation checklist. The data were analyzed using Statistical Packages for social Sciences (Version 24).

Results: The results revealed that overall level of preoperative nursing care was satisfied with mean score = (1.84), and Standard Deviation (± 0.70). And the overall the level of postoperative nursing care was good with mean score = (2.18), and standard deviation (± 0.78).

Conclusion: The study concluded that the overall level of preoperative nursing care was satisfied, and the overall level postoperative nursing care was good.

Recommendations: Improving the quality of nursing regarding preoperative nursing care. Further studies should be conducted concerning the quality of nursing care provided in all hospitals.

KEYWORDS: Quality of Nursing care, Preoperative nursing care, Postoperative nursing care.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Quality of care has become a critical issue in healthcare and will continue to be important as healthcare reforms. Quality is the degree to which consumers progress toward desired outcomes with the guidance and support of healthcare providers. Furthermore, Evan and Lindsay (2005) also defined it as the overall experience and satisfaction of patients with nursing services from the moment of admission until discharge ⁽¹⁾.

According to research, specific clinical quality measures are related to good nursing care. In addition, patients were aware that a strong relationship with a compassionate, knowledgeable, and competent nurse can significantly improve the comfort and effectiveness of hospital care. Also, nursing services are the backbone of the healthcare system in almost all countries worldwide. They represent between 60-70% of the healthcare personnel, is essential that we assess the quality of nursing care we offer to improve it ⁽²⁾. Nursing in general surgical departments plays a vital role in modern healthcare ⁽³⁾. Clients who undergo surgery may experience various consequences, including illness, discomfort, disability, and dissatisfaction ⁽⁴⁾.

Quality Nursing Care Provided to Surgical Patients Concerns and issues related to the quality of nursing care provided to surgical patients have motivated many researchers to conduct qualitative and quantitative studies on such an important issue. Some of these studies have focused on perceptions of nursing care in surgical settings ⁽³⁾. The assessment of nursing activities during the perioperative period is a crucial indicator in evaluating the implementation of the nursing care plan ⁽⁵⁾. Therefore, medical staff make necessary adjustments to improve nursing care practices during this period. Although surgery primarily involves the actions of the surgeons, nursing care is equally important. Excellent nursing care during the perioperative period can aid the patient in having the best possible conditions for the entire surgical process. Thus, the quality of the surgical procedure and nursing care plan are both essential factors in measuring the health of patient recovery. Nursing care plays a significant role in the perioperative setting, and the healthcare system fully monitors and evaluates the quality of healthcare provided to patients ⁽⁵⁾.

In general surgical wards, patients undergo two phases of nursing care: preoperative and postoperative nursing care. Nurses must meet the patient's needs and expectations for each phase of surgical care. The preoperative phase is the period of the surgical experience that begins with the client's admission and ends with the patient's transfer to the operating unit ⁽⁶⁾. During the preoperative phase, it is essential for a nurse to assess the patient, provide them with information about their condition, treatment options, surgical procedures, and evaluate them before surgery. The main objective of preoperative care is to assess the patient's readiness for surgery, identify the potential risks and dangers of surgery, advise the patient about the surgical procedure, and prepare them for post-operative experiences, home care planning, and emotional support ⁽⁶⁾.

Postoperative nursing care includes maintaining the airway, monitoring vital signs, assessing the effects of anesthetics, assessing the patient for complications, and providing comfort and pain relief ⁽⁶⁾. This is immediate post-operative care, usually provided in the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) before the patient is returned to the surgical unit. In addition to immediate post-operative nursing care, general postoperative care provided in the surgical unit focuses on promoting the patient's recovery, initiating teaching and monitoring care as well as such as necessary referrals for recovery and rehabilitation after hospital discharge ⁽⁷⁾.

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Surgical patients often experience anxiety and stress related to their surgery. Consequently, They have high expectations for nursing care and require extensive information about their conditions, procedures, treatment options, and post-surgery expectations ⁽⁷⁾. According to (NES, Omondil, 2017) Study conducted in Nairobi, Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH) considered knowledge of nursing care, as an important dimension of quality nursing care ⁽⁸⁾. Many factors prevent nurses from carrying out quality nursing care, such as a poor working environment, inadequate drug supply, nurses' shortage, increasing patient admissions, poor leadership, and a lack of equipment and materials. These factors lead to low-quality nursing care ⁽⁹⁾. Nowadays, healthcare organizations are more concerned about the quality of nursing care. Every healthcare industry is accountable to its patients. Consumers expect to

receive value for their money and rely on receiving high-quality services when needed. Patients now voice their concerns, make demands, file reports, and even take legal actions, recognizing the crucial role that nursing care plays in their outcomes. Furthermore, it is very important to measure patients' perception of the quality of nursing care in surgical wards of selected hospitals ⁽¹⁰⁾.

JUSTIFICATIONS:

The delivery of nursing care comprises a significant portion of all health services provided by healthcare organizations. Many health organizations and health institutions are striving to achieve high-quality services to attract more consumers ⁽¹¹⁾. Consequently, patients prefer to go to healthcare settings that have holistic nursing care and consider patients as the center of care ⁽¹²⁾. Previous studies confirmed that surgical patients have a high level of anxiety that would also affect the overall outcome of their health; nurses need to have the skills to provide care that would alleviate their anxiety ⁽¹³⁾. The overall goal stated by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Council of Nurses (ICN) is the highest possible level of health for all people, and providing high-quality care is one approach to reaching this goal. Measuring the quality of care in the healthcare organization has become increasingly important. Patients' perspectives on the quality of care depend on nursing care because nurses are involved in every aspect of patient care in a hospital ⁽¹⁴⁾. The significance of in-patients' perceptions of quality of care and their experiences has been highlighted in previous studies. Research has demonstrated that offering empowering preoperative information enhances the perception of perioperative care. Educational activities play a crucial role in empowering patients, especially among older individuals. Furthermore, patient education is essential for reducing preoperative anxiety and has a positive impact on the performance of healthcare professionals ⁽¹⁵⁾.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

General objective:

The general objective of this study is to assess the quality of nursing care for surgical patients.

Specific objectives:

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The specific objectives will be:

1. To measure the level of preoperative nursing care applied to the surgical patients admitted to general surgical wards.
2. To assess the level of postoperative nursing care provided to surgical patients.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

What is the level of pre and postoperative nursing care provided for surgical patients?

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study design

A descriptive cross-sectional hospital based study. was conducted during the period (Jan 2022 - Jan 2023).

2.2 Study area

The study was conducted in three selected main governmental teaching hospitals in Central Darfur state, South Darfur state, and West Darfur state (Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals).

Darfur region lies in western Sudan, which is approximately 493,180 km² in area and has a population of nearly six million. It comprises the states of North, West, South, East, and Central Darfur ⁽¹⁶⁾.

2.2.1. Zalingei Teaching Hospital:

The Zalingei Teaching Hospital is one of the biggest hospitals in Central Darfur state and was established in 1956. Located in the city center, west of the old mosque and south of the big market. it has an area of about 2000m². It consists of the Outpatient department, Radiology department, laboratory and blood bank department, Obstetric and Gynecological department, pediatrics department, operation and ICU department, Nutrition department, and General medical-surgical wards for male and female patients. It has 246 beds, 54 beds in the surgical wards, 131 nurses providing nursing care, and 53 nurses rotated for the male and female Medical -Surgical wards. The information mentioned above was collected from the statistics department in these hospitals.

2.2.2. Nyala Teaching Hospital:

The Nyala Teaching Hospital is located in central Nyala city. It is a tertiary and referral health facility that offers medical and surgical services referral from hospitals or clinics all around the state. It consists of many clinics and many wards such as emergency department, medical, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, and surgical wards, nursery unit, and two intensive care units. The total nurses worked in two shifts, 8 hours morning shift and 16 hours. Afternoon and night shift staff; the total number of nurses is 128 and 30 nurses provide care for patients admitted to male and female surgical wards. The information mentioned above was collected from the statistics department of this hospital.

2.2.3. Geneina Teaching Hospital:

The Geneina Teaching Hospital is located in the capital of West Darfur State at Geneina town, established in 1963 to teach medical and nursing students, train medical and nursing staff, and provide medical services to the community of West Darfur State and neighboring Chad and Central African Republic. It composed of eight wards (Male and Female Surgical wards, Male and Female medical wards, General pediatric ward, pediatric nutrition rehabilitation ward and obstetrical and gynecological ward consist of many units such as hemodialysis unit, dental unit, diabetic unit, and ICU unit. Surgical wards number of nurse = Female =12, Male =12 Total = 24 nurses. Number of bed = Male 28bed, Female = 28bed, Total = 56beds The information mentioned above was collected from statistics department in these hospital.

2.3 Study population:

Patients who were admitted to the general surgical wards of Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

2.3.1 Inclusion criteria:

The patients recruited in the study included those who:

- Adult patients of age group 18 years and above, admitted to the surgical wards in Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.
- Has had surgery performed under general or spinal anesthesia.
- Were in a stable general condition, fully conscious.

- Stayed in the ward for two or more days postoperatively.

2.3.2 Exclusion criteria:

Patients who were excluded from the study included those:

- Who were not operated on.
- Who did not consent to participate.
- Who were unable to communicate.
- Who had a burn injury or diabetic septic foot.

2.4 Sample size and sampling technique:

2.4.1 Sample size:

The researcher was selecting the sample for all patients who fulfilled the above criteria in surgical wards at Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

2.4.2 Sampling technique:

The study involved patients who were admitted to the general surgical wards of Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

The data collection instrument was:

Observational checklist to monitor the nurses' provision of nursing care to surgical patients.

2.5. Checklist: check lists to assess the level of preoperative nursing care and postoperative nursing care. Each checklist item has three answer options: a score of 3 indicates the item was done properly, a score of 2 indicates the item was done improperly, and a score of 1 indicates that the item was not done.

2.5.1 Section (1): Preoperative assessment checklist: consists of patient assessment, patient teaching, and patient preparation (24 points).

2.5.2 Section (2): Postoperative assessment checklist: consists of the assessment of immediate postoperative nursing care, routine postoperative nursing care, and postoperative home care teaching (29 points).

2.6 Validity:

The study tools were designed after an in-depth review of the literature. The draft was appraised by the supervisor. The instruments were subsequently reviewed by three expert committees to assess their appropriateness, accuracy, and representiveness.

Firstly, the tools were revised by the institutional review board of AL Neelain University. Second, the tools were revised by three related academic staff: one surgeon from a surgical department, one nursing expert, and one statistician to test the clarity, feasibility, and applicability of the instruments.

2.7 Reliability:

The study reliability analysis was undertaken to measure the consistency, stability, and repeatability of the instrument. A pilot study was done on 10 patients (10%) of the total sample to check the reliability of the instrument. We find that the reliability of the checklist is 95%, which indicates the excellent credibility of the participants in their answers to the questions of the checklist. The stability coefficient is defined as the degree of stability of the results based on the analysis of the observational checklist if we take another sample, and this (97%) indicates the strength of the stability of the results of the sample members participating in the checklist.

2.8 Ethical clearance of the study

The researcher followed many steps to accomplish the ethical clearance.

- Ethical approval was obtained from the research ethics committee and institutional review board of the faculty of graduate studies and scientific research at Alneelain University.
- Official letters were obtained from the Ministry of Health in Central Darfur State, South Darfur State, and West Darfur State. Then, formal headed letters were sent to the managers of selected hospitals.
- Verbal informed consent was obtained individually from each participant after explaining the purpose and justification of the study in clear and simple terms. The name of the participant was not required; a serial number was used instead. The participation was completely voluntary. The participant had the option to accept or reject and had the right to withdraw at any time. The data were kept confidential and retained for three years; it was discarded after three years.

3. RESULTS

This chapter analyzes and interprets data collected to assess the quality of nursing care for surgical patients. The collected data were coded, analyzed, and organized into tables and graphs, then interpreted based on the research objectives and questions.

Section (1): Quality of preoperative nursing care.

Table (3.1): Evaluation of preoperative patient assessment.

(N = 95).

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Take a medical history from a patient	Count	46	32	17	1.69	0.76
	Row N %	48%	34%	18%		
Perform a physical examination on the patient.	Count	29	39	27	1.98	0.77
	Row N %	31%	41%	28%		
Witnessed the patient signing the informed consent.	Count	69	16	10	1.38	0.67
	Row N %	73%	17%	11%		
Assess the patient for any allergies.	Count	25	34	36	2.12	0.80
	Row N %	26%	36%	38%		
Assessed the patient's nutritional status.	Count	24	29	42	2.19	0.82
	Row N %	25%	31%	44%		
Assess the patient's knowledge about the disease.	Count	73	19	3	1.26	0.51
	Row N %	77%	20%	3%		
Total	Count	44	28	23	1.77	0.72
	Row N %	46%	30%	24%		

Figure (3.1): The overall preoperative patient assessment. (N = 95).

Table (3.2): Assessment of the preoperative patient education.

(N = 95).

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Train the patient to perform deep breathing and coughing exercises.	Count	16	22	57	2.43	0.77
	Row N %	17%	23%	60%		
Teach the patient about the importance of mobilization after surgery.	Count	26	20	49	2.24	0.86
	Row N %	27%	21%	52%		
Instruct the patient how to use the incentive spirometer device.	Count	13	7	75	2.65	0.71
	Row N %	14%	7%	79%		
Teach the patient about the importance of leg exercises and how to do them postoperatively.	Count	21	25	49	2.29	0.81
	Row N %	22%	26%	52%		
Inform the patient that they may come out of the operation with some tubes.	Count	35	10	50	2.16	0.94
	Row N %	37%	11%	52%		
Tell the patient that they will feel pain after the operation, but they will receive analgesics.	Count	37	21	37	2.00	0.89
	Row N %	39%	22%	39%		
Total	Count	25	18	53	2.30	0.83
	Row N %	26%	18%	56%		

Figure (3.2): The overall preoperative patient education. (N = 95).

Table (3.3): The preoperative patient preparation.

(N = 95).

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gather and interpret the results of diagnostic tests.	Count	53	39	3	1.47	0.56
	Row N %	56%	41%	3%		
Ensure that all necessary blood work and other tasks are completed.	Count	85	9	1	1.12	0.35
	Row N %	89%	9%	1%		
Notify the patient to withhold food and fluid at least 6 – 8 hours before surgery.	Count	90	5	0	1.05	0.22
	Row N %	95%	5%	0%		
Insert a urinary catheter if indicated.	Count	82	10	3	1.17	0.45
	Row N %	86%	11%	3%		
Prepare the bowel by using a laxative and enema if prescribed.	Count	80	12	3	1.19	0.47
	Row N %	84%	13%	3%		
Clean and sterilize the surgical site	Count	32	20	43	2.12	0.89
	Row N %	34%	21%	45%		
Pick up the surgical gown	Count	42	47	6	1.62	0.60

	Row N %	44%	49%	6%		
Give the preoperative medications and fluids	Count	47	14	34	1.86	0.92
	Row N %	49%	15%	36%		
Lock the patient's valuables in a secure cupboard or give them to their family.	Count	74	14	7	1.29	0.60
	Row N %	78%	15%	7%		
Support the patient by relieving anxiety	Count	27	44	24	1.97	0.74
	Row N %	28%	46%	25%		
Make sure the file is completed	Count	54	40	1	1.44	0.52
	Row N %	57%	42%	1%		
Handle the patient to the theatre with all their documents	Count	85	8	2	1.13	0.39
	Row N %	89%	9%	2%		
Total	Count	63	21	11	1.45	0.56
	Row N %	66%	23%	11%		

Figure (3.3): The overall preoperative patient preparation. (N = 95).

Table (3.4): The overall preoperative nursing care.

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Preoperative patient assessment	Count	44	28	23	1.77	0.72
	Row N %	46%	30%	24%		
Assessment of the preoperative teaching	Count	25	18	53	2.30	0.83
	Row N %	26%	18%	56%		
The preoperative patient preparation	Count	63	21	11	1.45	0.56
	Row N %	66%	23%	11%		
Total	Count	132	67	87	1.84	0.70
	Row N %	46.2%	23.4%	30.4%		

Figure (3.4): The overall preoperative nursing care.

Section (2): Quality of postoperative nursing care.

Table (3.5): The immediate postoperative nursing assessment.

(N = 95).

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Position patient to enhance comfort, safety.	Count	47	19	29	1.81	0.88
	Row N %	49%	20%	31%		
Assess patient using ABCs methods.	Count	14	11	70	2.59	0.74
	Row N %	15%	12%	73%		
Assess level of consciousness, orientation, and ability to move extremities.	Count	16	15	64	2.51	0.77
	Row N %	17%	16%	67%		
Monitor vital signs and note skin warmth, moisture, and cold.	Count	30	18	47	2.18	0.89
	Row N %	32%	19%	49%		
Make sure the tubes in place and connect all drainage tubes to gravity or suction.	Count	35	29	31	1.96	0.84
	Row N %	37%	31%	32%		
Assess the surgical site and wound drainage systems.	Count	28	32	35	2.07	0.82
	Row N %	29%	34%	37%		
Check the patient file and medication ordered	Count	55	31	9	1.52	0.67
	Row N %	58%	33%	9%		
Assess pain level, pain characteristics (location, quality) and timing, type and route of administration of last pain medication	Count	28	37	30	2.02	0.79
	Row N %	29%	39%	32%		
Assess IV sites for patency and infusion for correct rate of solution.	Count	63	26	6	1.40	0.61
	Row N %	66%	27%	6%		
Administer analgesics as prescribed and assess their effectiveness in relieving pain.	Count	44	41	10	1.64	0.67
	Row N %	46%	43%	11%		

Assess urine output in closed drainage system or the patient urge to void and bladder distention.	Count	27	22	46	2.20	0.86
	Row N %	28%	23%	48%		
Maintains measures to prevent DVT.	Count	19	23	53	2.36	0.80
	Row N %	20%	24%	56%		
Provide information to patient and family.	Count	31	43	21	1.89	0.74
	Row N %	33%	45%	22%		
Total	Count	34	27	35	2.01	0.77
	Row N %	35%	28%	36%		

Figure (3.5): The overall immediate postoperative nursing assessment. (N = 95).

Table (3.6): Routine postoperative nursing interventions.

(N = 95).

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Assist the patient during ambulation and exercise	Count	20	13	62	2.44	0.82
	Row N %	21%	14%	65%		
Assess patient for tolerance to pain	Count	14	24	57	2.45	0.74
	Row N %	15%	25%	60%		
Assess continuation of medication administration as ordered.	Count	44	30	21	1.76	0.80
	Row N %	46%	32%	22%		
Monitoring of vital signs	Count	33	18	44	2.12	0.90
	Row N %	35%	19%	46%		
Assess of bowel sound to established for feeding	Count	13	10	72	2.62	0.72
	Row N %	14%	11%	75%		
Assessment of surgical complications	Count	12	25	58	2.48	0.71
	Row N %	13%	26%	61%		
Calculate intake and output chart	Count	21	9	65	2.46	0.84
	Row N %	22%	9%	68%		
Maintain aseptic technique and infection control standard.	Count	20	40	35	2.16	0.75
	Row N %	21%	42%	37%		
Document & report the pt.'s conditions.	Count	17	23	55	2.40	0.78
	Row N %	18%	24%	58%		
Total	Count	22	21	52	2.32	0.78
	Row N %	23%	22%	55%		

Figure (3.6): The routine postoperative nursing interventions. (N = 95).

Table (3.7): Postoperative nursing home care teaching.

(N = 95).

Item		Done correctly	Done properly	Improperly done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Teach the patient about exercise.	Count	20	40	35	2.16	0.75
	Row N %	21%	42%	37%		
Maneuvers for how to use assisting device in home care	Count	11	24	60	2.52	0.70
	Row N %	12%	25%	63%		
Assess Patient condition or functional status at discharge	Count	18	22	55	2.39	0.79
	Row N %	19%	23%	58%		
Inform patient of medications prescribed at discharge	Count	44	18	33	1.88	0.90
	Row N %	46%	19%	35%		
Teach the patient about wound care.	Count	30	37	28	1.98	0.79
	Row N %	32%	39%	29%		
Teach the patient about diet.	Count	10	21	64	2.57	0.68
	Row N %	11%	22%	67%		
Teach the patient regarding regular follow-up	Count	41	18	36	1.95	0.90
	Row N %	43%	19%	38%		
Total	Count	25	26	44	2.21	0.79
	Row N %	26%	27%	47%		

Figure (3.7): The overall postoperative nursing home care teaching. (N = 95).

Table (3.8): The overall postoperative nursing care.

Item		Done properly	Improperly done	Not done	Mean	Standard Deviation
Immediate postoperative nursing assessment	Count	34	27	35	2.01	0.77
	Row N %	35%	28%	36%		
Routine postoperative nursing interventions	Count	22	21	52	2.32	0.78
	Row N %	23%	22%	55%		
Postoperative nursing home care teaching	Count	25	26	44	2.21	0.79
	Row N %	26%	27%	47%		
Total	Count	81	74	131	2.18	0.78
	Row N %	28.3%	25.9%	45.8		

Figure (3.8): The overall postoperative nursing care.

DISCUSSION:

This study aims to assess the quality of nursing care for surgical patients. The preoperative patient assessment in the current study showed that the majority (77.0%) of participants were knowledgeable about the disease, and 46% of the overall preoperative patient assessment was considered good. In contrast, participants who received preoperative education from nurses were 1.15 times more likely to be satisfied with preoperative nursing care than those who did not receive such education from nurses. This finding differs from the study conducted at the University of Gondar referral hospital and public hospitals in Addis Ababa ⁽¹⁷⁾. Study conducted by (A damson et al., 2012) Many surgical patients were not adequately prepared physically and emotionally for the surgery despite the fact previous studies suggested the need to prepare patients emotionally before surgery ⁽⁴⁾. Regarding the overall assessment of preoperative teaching, the current study revealed that more than half (56%) of the study participants don't teach about the procedures. Regarding the preoperative preparation checklist, the current study found that (66%) of the study participants were adequately prepared. The results of the study regarding the overall

preoperative nursing care checklist, the current study revealed that nearly half (46.2%) of the study participants had proper preoperative nursing care. On contrast the overall satisfaction with preoperative nursing care among patients who have undergone surgical procedures at Wolaita Sodo University Comprehensive Specialized Hospital was 79.5% (75.4–83.6) ⁽¹⁸⁾. another study showed that the overall patient perception regarding quality of perioperative nursing care was moderately good, with a score of 113.0 ± 21.4 . The study finding was different with those of the previous studies examining patients' perceptions regarding quality of care ⁽¹⁸⁾. A study done by, Dönmez et al. reported that quality of perioperative nursing care scores of surgical patients were 128.2 ± 1.2 ⁽¹⁹⁾.

Regarding the immediate postoperative nursing assessment checklist, the current study showed that the majority (73% and 67%) of the study participants didn't assess ABCs and (level of consciousness, orientation, and ability to move extremities), respectively. the current study revealed that (46%) of nurses assessed the pain level and characteristics, which is similar to the survey done by Cadogan and associates, which found that less than half (48%) of patients, nurses had ever asked them about their pain ⁽²⁰⁾.

Regarding the overall immediate postoperative nursing care assessment checklist, the current study revealed that (35%) of the study participants didn't assess the patient immediately. In the recent study, the majority of participants (65%, 60%, 75%, and 68%) did not assist patients with ambulation and exercise, assess them for pain tolerance, check bowel sounds, and calculate intake and output charts as part of the routine postoperative nursing intervention checklist. Regarding the overall routine postoperative interventions, the current study revealed that more than half (55%) of the study participants didn't perform routine postoperative interventions. Regarding the postoperative home care teaching checklist, the current study revealed that (63% and 67%) of the study participants don't teach about maneuvers to use assisting devices in the home care and diet, respectively. The current study regarding overall postoperative nursing care showed that (45.8%) of the study participants don't perform postoperative nursing care.

Limitations of the study:

- The convenience sample techniques used in this study prevent the results from being broadly applicable.
- Another limitation of the study was that the sample was limited to surgical patients in selected governmental teaching hospitals in the Darfur region.

CONCLUSION:

According to the finding of the present study, the following can be concluded:

- The overall mean scores of quality of nursing care regarding the level of preoperative nursing care were satisfied ($M = 1.84, SD = \pm 0.70$).
- The overall mean scores of quality of nursing care regarding the level of postoperative nursing care were good ($M = 2.18, SD = \pm 0.78$).

RECOMMENDATIONS:

According to the basis of the present study, the following are recommended:

- Further studies should be conducted concerning patient quality of nursing care provided for surgical patients in all hospitals.
- Improving the quality of nursing care should focus more on preoperative nursing care, mainly preoperative teaching. And in postoperative nursing care focus on routine postoperative nursing interventions and postoperative home care teaching.
- Continuous training programs based on evidence-based guidelines will significantly improve the quality of nursing care by establishing continuous professional development programs.
- Hospital authority and nursing administration need to motivate, support, and encourage the nursing staff to attend training programs and workshops related to the quality of nursing care for surgical patients by providing all facilities to them.

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